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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****SELF-MEDICATION AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS****Zahra Khalid, Maryam Zahoor, Ushna Riaz**

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Article Received: March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

Self-medication is widely practiced worldwide and often considered as a component of self-care. However, unlike other components of self-care, self-medication has the potential to do good as well as cause harm since it involves the use of drugs. A total of 100 students was included in the study. The mean age of the students was 21.12 ± 1.23 years. There were 50 (50%) females and 50 (50%) males in the study. According to 30% of the students, they have never done self-medication. Seventy percent responded that for common diseases they use medication on their own. A lot of medical students are involved in self-medication. Education regarding this issue should also be taken into consideration because self-medication among future healthcare professionals can represent a serious threat to professionalism in medicine and it has potential to put at risk public trust into this profession.

Keywords: *Self-medication, medical students*

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INTRODUCTION:

It is common for people to feel unwell, and human beings have an inherent tendency to use herbs, potions, medications, etc. for treating themselves. Everyday people throughout the world act on their own for their health; they practice self-care. In some instances, they do so through self-medication, which is now increasingly being considered as a component of self-care. Some governments are increasingly encouraging self-care of minor illnesses, including self-medication. Self-medication can be defined as obtaining and consuming drugs without the advice of a physician for diagnosis, prescription or surveillance of treatment. Self-medication differs from self-care in that it involves drugs that may do good or cause harm.³ In several studies it has been found that inappropriate self-medication causes wastage of resources, increases resistance of pathogens and generally causes serious health hazards such as adverse drug reactions, prolonged suffering and drug dependence (1,2).

Self-medication is widely practiced worldwide and often considered as a component of self-care. However, unlike other components of self-care, self-medication has the potential to do good as well as cause harm since it involves the use of drugs. The World Health Organization (WHO) has appropriately pointed out that responsible self-medication can help prevent and treat diseases that do not require medical consultation and provides a cheaper alternative for treating common illnesses. The practice of self-medication must be based on authentic medical information otherwise irrational use of drugs can cause wastage of resources, increased resistance of pathogens, and can lead to serious health hazards such as adverse drug reaction

and prolonged morbidity. In developing countries, self-medication is a common practice as it provides a low-cost alternative for people who cannot afford the high cost of clinical service and also as many drugs are dispensed over the counter without prescription from a registered medical practitioner (3,4).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was conducted in different medical colleges of Pakistan. The data was collected from students of different classes on a predefined proforma. Different Likert type questions were asked. All the responses were collected and analyzed in SPSS Ver. 25.0. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. Relevant statistical analysis was performed.

RESULTS:

A total of 100 students was included in the study. The mean age of the students was 21.12 ± 1.23 years, mean age of the females was 20.23 ± 0.13 years and mean age of males was 23.89 ± 2.31 years. There were 50 (50%) females and 50 (50%) males in the study. According to 30% of the students, they have never done self-medication i.e. whenever they are ill, they consult a regular doctor and use medication after proper prescription. Seventy percent responded that for common diseases they use medication on their own. When asked about common diseases, they responded i.e. fever, cough, flu, menstrual pain, diarrhea, constipation, headache, and body aches etc. When asked about the reason of self-medication, they provided certain reasons i.e. living in the hostels, general physician is away from the residence, doctor charges etc.

DISCUSSION:

Self-medication is an important issue among population of medical students. Self-medication in the research sample is connected with female gender, older age, lower level of father's education, consumption of alcoholic beverages, possession of home-pharmacies, physical inactivity and depressive symptoms and their tolerability. People may disuse drugs in the form of getting medications of others who told them that they have improved when they had taken those medications. They also may repeat a previous prescription. In economically deprived countries most episodes of illness are treated by self-medication. In a number of developing countries many drugs are dispensed over the counter without medical supervision. Therefore, self-medication provides a lower cost-alternative for people who cannot afford the cost of clinical service. Studies revealed that the increase in self-medication was due to a number of factors. These included socioeconomic factors, lifestyle, ready access to drugs, the increased potential to manage certain illnesses through self-care, and greater availability of medicinal products (1,5).

Self-medication with antibiotics has the potential to produce harmful effects on the society, as well as, on individual patients. This may be due to the fact that antibiotics can be obtained from pharmacies without the requirement of a prescription even though antibiotics are prescription-only-medicine. Additionally, antibiotics can be supplied by friends, relatives and other ways. In developing countries most illnesses are treated by self-medication. There are some reports of antibiotic self-medication in Pakistan and some other countries (2,3,5).

CONCLUSION:

A lot of medical students are involved in self-medication. Education regarding this issue should

also be taken into consideration because self-medication among future healthcare professionals can represent a serious threat to professionalism in medicine and it has potential to put at risk public trust into this profession.

Conflict of Interest:

There is no conflict of interest

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